

Multifunctional landscape design with agroforestry

Introduction of agroforestry systems on agricultural land should be carefully planned and an economic investigation of local demand for timber/biomass and an environmental analysis of afforestation demand should be carried out beforehand. Bearing in mind the need to maintain green infrastructure in agricultural landscape and carry out effective and consistent actions with the aim to protect soil and water, it is recommended to design agroforestry systems in line with the applicable law, local land development plans and strategies of adaptation to climate change. Such actions will contribute to improving the effectiveness of delivering ecosystem services. Otherwise, soil and waters may be exposed to degradation and result in decrease of profitability of agricultural production. Last but not least, it is important to select the right plants and suitable for the neighbour vegetation as well.

Figure 1. Network of woodlands, shelterbelts, buffer strips and agroforestry systems should be created based on afforestation needs of the local area: protection against soil erosion (A), water evapotranspiration (B), flooding (C) and nutrients leaching (D). Connections between all the elements maintain green infrastructure in the agricultural landscape and in this way improve biodiversity (based on *Arbre et Paysage 32* - <http://www.ap32.fr/page01.html>, modified by J. Józefczuk, In: Kujawa A., Kujawa K., Zajączkowski J., Borek R., Tyszkochmielowiec P., Józefczuk J., Krukowska-Szopa I., Śliwa P., Witkoś-Gnach K., 2019 – EcoDevelopment Foundation <http://drzewa.org.pl/publikacja/1655-2/zadrzewienia-na-obszarach-wiejskichpodglad>)

What you should look for when establishing agroforestry system?

The best method of establishing agroforestry systems takes into account the following environmental conditions and risks at the landscape scale, resulting in the subsequent needs:

- 1) Water losses due to evapotranspiration from crops cultivated in low forestation areas with a significant share of light soils;
- 2) Soil losses (from fine sands, silt and dry peat layers) in areas exposed wind erosion;
- 3) Soil losses on slopes exposed to water erosion;
- 4) Watercourses and reservoirs existing near arable fields;
- 5) Biodiversity losses (enemies of pests or pollinators) in sparsely wooded areas (afforestation <15%) with a high share of arable land (>75%) and

lack of connections between at least 20% of the refuge areas, existing in the agricultural landscape;

- 6) Local conservation needs in the agricultural farm (securing slopes, reducing noise pollution, particulate matter emissions and noxious smells, protection of pastures against wind, etc.).

Each problem needs specific solution. Therefore, the environmental risks should be minimized as far as possible by careful implementation of set of measures to be operating in most effective way. Introduction of agroforestry systems shall not be considered in one-size-fits-all approach. As far as reasonable practical, woody species should be carefully selected, grouped and maintained in a proper design (vertical and horizontal) taking into account local conditions to improve production efficiency.

How to effectively introduce trees in an agricultural landscape?

The main need of the particular area defines the requirements concerning orientation of tree rows, planning the understorey layer, the width of greensward within shelterbelts, share of fruit and thorny species of trees and bushes as well as diversification of their flowering periods. For each need there are specific recommendations:

- 1) The protection range of shelterbelts (reduction of wind speed by at least 10%) is directly proportional to its height. Under optimal conditions the protection range may exceed the trees height even twenty times (20h). Windbreaks should be perpendicular to the prevailing wind direction, with additional cross strips, connected to them (figure 2). The most effective are wide, double-row barriers, with not too dense crown leaf horizontal density (with 20-30% in the canopy of full-grown trees). It is also important to include bushes in the understorey layer (figure 3).

Figure 2. Optimum spatial orientation and distances for the network of shelterbelts designed to mitigate evapotranspiration and wind erosion on adjacent crop fields (J. Zajęczkowski).

Figure 3. Optimal structure of tree row is a crucial factor to reduce effectively wind-induced erosion and evapotranspiration at landscape scale (J. Zajęczkowski).

- 2) The distance between the main barriers (from 12- up to 18-fold of the target height) depends on the risk of wind erosion phenomena in the particular area. In winter, when the risk of wind erosion is the greatest, the effectiveness of

the wind barrier decreases, hence the need to keep two rows of trees and a complementary layer of bushes in the understory.

- 3) Shelterbelts against water erosion should be several metres wide, rows arranged across the slope, spaced at intervals of 300 m in case of short slopes or up to 200 m on longer slopes, both with well-developed sward to prevent surface runoff.
- 4) Along watercourses and reservoirs the strip of greensward should be at least 10 m wide, with loosely distributed trees preventing the runoff of pollutants (e.g. fertilisers) from the field (figure 4). The trees shouldn't be planted closer than 20 m from active drainage ditches.

Figure 4. Buffer strips along sides of water reservoirs should comprise wide grass strip with loosely distributed trees (K. Zajęczkowski).

- 5) Agroforestry systems should be arranged in a way that makes it possible to connect them (e.g. along roads, watercourses or field margins) with the already existing groves, shelterbelts, water bodies or old parks (figure 1). To improve biocenotic conditions it is necessary to create a network of thin corridors up to 500m long, connected to net nodes. Agroforestry systems should have a varied species composition of trees and bushes, melliferous and fruit species are highly recommended.
- 6) To secure slopes, species with extensive root system should be chosen. It is also important they have rich foliage to provide high amounts of organic matter to the soil. Relatively wide and high strips of trees with bushes in the

understorey with thick canopy may help protect against dust particles and noxious smells. To reduce noise pollution, usually spruce is used (figure 5).

Figure 5. Spruce works perfectly for reduction of noise pollution (J. Zajączkowski).

Above recommendations might be not in accordance to standard recommendations for agroforestry systems (optimal orientation of rows North-South maximally reducing light competition to crops or optimal design in terms of trees species productivity) or attitude of farmers towards mono-species trees production. These restrictions should take into account numerous trade-offs in the individual decision processes.

Figure 6. Hawthorn is melliferous plant providing number of food products, including honey however is not recommended to be planted nearby orchards (Heildebergerin/pixabay.com).

For design of agroforestry system, it is advised to use native species and already adapted to local conditions. Companion plants are welcomed. Due to the risk of transmitting crop diseases, rose bushes (especially hawthorn, figure 6) are not recommended for orchards, nor is barberry suitable in the proximity of cereal crops. Some bushes shouldn't be planted near field and horticultural crops, as they provoke occurrence of aphids. Invasive and toxic tree and shrub species should also be avoided.

When planting trees, bear in mind the canopy size of a full-grown tree and maximum extent of roots, especially when they are located near the field margin – in such cases planting should be consulted with the owner of the adjacent land. The same rule applies to planting alongside road, where it can be incompatible with the provisions of law.

Only spatially continuous and properly designed shelterbelts/hedgerows network is capable to effectively mitigate large-scale environmental threats. Agroforestry should contribute to coherent vision of sustainable rural development through rational management of natural resources building on local needs of ecosystems and expectations of farmers.

Further information

Zajączkowski J and Zajączkowski K (2015) Trees outside forest in Poland. Papers on Global Change IGBP 22: 53-62

Zajączkowski J and Zajączkowski K (2013) Silviculture. Trees outside forest (in Polish). Ed. PWRiL, Warszawa: 174

Zajączkowski J and Zajączkowski K (2009) Farmland afforestations: new goals and guidelines for Poland, Fol. For. Pol. Ser. A - Forestry, vol. 51(1), 5-11

Zajączkowski K (2005) Regionalization of agricultural landscape needs for shelterbelts and woodlots in Poland (in Polish), Papers of Forest Research Institute, Monographs 4: 131

Zajączkowski K, Talalaj Z, Węgorek T and Zajączkowska B (2001) The selection of trees and shrubs for rural areas afforestation (in Polish). Ed. Forest Research Institute, Sękocin: 78

This technical sheet was compiled by Robert Borek (IUNG-PIB - Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation in Puławy, Poland) and Jacek Zajączkowski (SGGW – Warsaw University of Life Sciences) within the context of the European project SustainFARM.

Puławy, March 2019